

A LECTURE DEMONSTRATION OF OSMOSIS

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In a previous communication by the author, a lecture experiment on gas diffusion using Cartesian divers was described (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 79). The diver has been found also suitable for a demonstration of the phenomenon of osmosis as well.

A glass tube 18 cm. in length and 3.5 cm. in diameter or a short glass chimney, containing a molar solution of pure common salt or cane sugar, without air bubbles and with a coloured diver floating in it, is closed on one side by a semi-permeable membrane, and on the other by a rubber bung carrying a tap with a long stem of narrow bore (1.5 to 2 mm.). The diver, filled with the solution is retained above the tap, after removing any excess by loosening the tap key.

When the membrane part is dipped in pure water in a dish, with the tap open, and when leaks are absent, the solution rises quickly in the narrow tube, as the membrane used allows rapid osmosis. Some of the solution above the tap is now forced down by air from the lungs, until the diver acquires a density just insufficient for diving, and the tap is then closed. On surrounding the membrane alternately with pure water and a saturated solution of pure common salt (about 6 molar), the diver sinks down and then rises up, as a result of the direct and reversed osmosis produced. The experiment does not exceed ten minutes' time. Finally, with water in the dish and the tap open, the solution may be allowed to rise in the tube and overflow.

The membrane used is the tough and the transparent cellulose paper, taken from the wrappers of cigarette packets or other source. It is rinsed in spirit, soaked in distilled water for some hours, washed, and tied to the mouth of the tube with the edges closed over a layer of paraffin wax. Any possible leaks are stopped by an external coating of the paraffin.

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Received August 26, 1945
